

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		27-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Nielsen et al.	
Country of origin		Denmark	
Publication year		2008	
Title of article		Costs and quality of life for prehabilitation and early rehabilitation after surgery of the lumbar spine	
Title of journal		BMC Health Services Research	
Volume 8	Issue 209	Pages 1-7	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	60 patients undergoing lumbar fusion for degenerative lumbar disease	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of intervention	Type: Integrated program including prehabilitation and early rehabilitation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of comparison	The standard care programme	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of outcome measures	Quality of life, costs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 3,

INCLUDE EXCLUDE

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To compare the economic impact and quality of life of surgery for degenerative lumbar spine disease with and without integration of prehabilitation and early rehabilitation	p. 2
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	The present study included data collected in a randomised controlled trial	p. 2
Start date	Not reported	
End date	Not reported	
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear The study was performed in accordance with the Helsinki II Declaration, and all patients participated after informed consent. The Regional Scientific Ethical Committee 01-041/03 approved the protocol, and the study has been registered in the international protocol registration system http://www.ClinicalTrials.gov , ID NCT 00459966	p. 3

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	Not reported	
Inclusion criteria	Not reported	
Exclusion criteria	Not reported	
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear All patients participated after informed consent.	p. 2

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Integrated programme	Abstract, p. 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=28 (M:11, F:17) Mean age = 48	p. 2, table 1 p. 2 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Content: Extra resources for prehabilitation; information and instruction, optimisation of pain treatment in relation to the 6-weeks home training program of 30 minutes per day followed-up by phone calls and log-books, 6-weeks smoking cessation program with free nicotine replacement therapy and weekly follow-up visits, 4-weeks alcohol abstinence programme with free medication (benzodiazepines, disulfiram and B-vitamins) and weekly follow-up visits. Postoperatively, the integrated programme included double the time for physiotherapy during their stay at hospital, protein-rich drinks, balanced and patient-controlled epidural analgesia and a follow-up visits for smokers and harmful drinkers.	p. 2-3

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Standard care programme	Abstract, p. 2-6
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=32 (M:13, F:19) Mean age = 52	p. 2 table 1 p. 2 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Standard care program: Not specified in details.	

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)

Outcome name	Quality of life	p. 3
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	The generic Quality of life survey tool 15D No difference	p. 3

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	Costs	p. 2
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	<p>The costs originated from three categories; staff resources, equipment and purely bed costs. The bed costs included salary of the nurses and porters, food, clothes, laundry and cleaning.</p> <p>The costs were estimated from multiplication of the resource consumption and unit costs. The focus was on the differences between the two programmes. For that reason, the identical costs for the primary operation and related medication during hospital stay for the two programmes were not included in this analysis.</p>	p. 2-3

Follow up

Follow up	6 months	p. 3, p. 5 table 3
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)

